

DESIRABLE OR UNDESIRABLE: ATTITUDE AND BEHAVIOR OF STUDENTS TOWARD TRANSITIONING FROM ONLINE TO FACE-TO-FACE MODE OF LEARNING

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Desirable or Undesirable: Attitude and Behavior of Students toward Transitioning from Online to Face-to-Face Mode of Learning

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Abstract

This study investigated constructs concerning the adjustment of the students regarding the transition from the online to the face-to-face mode of learning during the COVID-19 pandemic period. The research participants included all twenty teachers at the junior high school department of Saint Theresa's College of Cebu during the academic year 2022-2023. The research instrument employed was a set of questionnaires with open-ended questions referring to the three constructs of the study. A thematic analysis of the qualitative data gathered from the questionnaire was done. The results of the data gathered consisted of the different themes that emerged from the clustering of the significant statements revealed by the teacher participants about the adjustment in school of their students during the transition period. For the construct on attitude and behavior of the students, two themes emerged, namely, desirable and undesirable attitudes and behavior of the students. The emergent themes for the construct on problems and challenges have the following categories: academic; disciplinary; financial; and psychological. The third and last construct of the study on the coping mechanisms of the students has its emergent themes with the following categories: academic; recreational; discipline and organization; and socialization. The results of the study obtained would help in the needs assessment and the provision of background information for the teachers and the guidance counselor's assistance in enabling the students to adjust during the transition from online to face-to-face mode of learning.

Keywords: *COVID-19 pandemic, transition from online to face-to-face, attitude and behavior, problems and challenges, coping mechanism, qualitative study*

Introduction

The Philippine educational system has been following the set-up of holding classes in a physical environment way back from time immemorial. Teachers and learners are into face-to-face interactions which promote academic stimulation and socialization. This has been the traditional practice in the Philippine educational system. In the year 2019, however, the case of the coronavirus disease was first reported to the World Health Organization (WHO) on December 31 of the said year. On March 11, 2020, the WHO declared the outbreak of coronavirus disease as a global concern, designating the term COVID-19 for the disease (Akojie et al., 2022). The COVID-19 pandemic brought drastic changes to the different sectors of society, including that of the field of education (Beruin, 2022).

The COVID-19 pandemic has brought a huge effect on the Philippine education system (Cui et al., 2023). It has contributed to a change from the conventional and traditional mode of learning to a more complicated yet modern way of teaching and learning, that is, with the use of technology catering to distance learning (Kasperski & Balu, 2023; Tulaskar et al., 2022). This is to address the need to continue the education process despite the pandemic faced by the country and by the world (Treceñe, 2022). Although the advantage of the online system in pursuing the education process during the pandemic is valuable, the system has its share of challenges (Najjar et al., 2022). Mental health has been an issue due to the frustration of being trapped at home for an indefinite period (Reimers, 2022). Due to issues in mental health, adaptive mechanisms to changes during the pandemic have become a problem. This includes the ability, or lack thereof, of the students to adjust to the new online setup (Cabello, 2022).

With the current improvement in the state of the COVID-19 pandemic, there is a gradual trend to go back to the traditional mode of onsite classes (Roy et al., 2023). This transition also brings about problems in the adjustment of the students. The students are exhibiting certain attitudes and behaviors, as well as problems that affect their coping mechanisms to the changes in the educational set-up. Educators must turn their attention to what matters in the classroom, that is, student learning and well-being (Cabello & Bonotan, 2021). Therefore, it would be beneficial to conduct a study that would investigate the root causes of the problems directed to the adjustment of the students during the transition period from online to face-to-face mode of learning. This precisely is the aim of this present study.

Online Mode of Learning

The online mode of learning has its advantages and disadvantages. The advantages of online learning include the following: information accessibility, flexibility, cost-effectiveness, and learning at one's phase (Abucejo et al., 2022). On the other hand, the disadvantages are the following: personal preferences; lack of high-speed internet connection; lack of concentration; limited interpersonal communications and sense of belongingness; and psychological problems arising from frustration at being unable to leave home for an extended period (Bahinting et al., 2022).

The Need to Return to Face-to-Face Mode of Learning

At present, we have slowly felt that the pandemic seems to come to its end, and our life also is slowly going back to the way it used to

be little by little (Plotnikof et al., 2022). With this, there is also a need to pay attention to the transition of the students back to face-to-face education and its implications on the student's attitude and behavior toward learning after being so acquainted with the online or modular setup (Samortin et al., 2022). The process of going back from online to face-to-face classes also poses a lot of challenges to the school, teachers, and students (Ando et al., 2022).

The disadvantages of online learning, as earlier mentioned, brought about adverse psychological effects on the students (Riconalla et al., 2022). The students may not have yet fully recovered from the effects of the educational changes during the height of the pandemic and now have to go back to the face-to-face set-up which will entail another problem in adapting to the newer trend (Olleras et al., 2022). The students are then faced with another shift of learning modality which at this time around, is the co-existence with the COVID-19 virus within the return to physical educational set-up.

Transition from Online to Face-to-Face Mode of Learning

The education system requires that schools slowly resume the physical set-up to bridge the learning gap during the online distance so that quality education will presently be delivered (Tagare, 2023). The abrupt transition of learning modalities has affected the students' behavior both in a desirable and undesirable manner (Brzezinska et al., 2022).

Desirable behaviors are those behaviors that are taught in best practices, showing appropriate demeanor during classes and even in and out of the classroom. This positive behavior can foster a positive and conducive learning environment (Elrod et al., 2022). This also leads to a smoother transfer of the learning process from the teacher to the learners. In the presence of desirable behaviors, the majority of the students tend to progress more from being physically present in school because, in school, they have more chances to exhibit a sense of collaboration among their classmates and learning becomes more fun and enjoyable (Beruin, 2022). Undesirable behaviors, on the other hand, are those disruptive behaviors of the students in class. This type of behavior can affect not only the individual student concerned but also the other students and the teachers. Disruptive behavior can interrupt the teaching-learning process. The students who demonstrate disruptive classroom behavior may have needs that are different from the other learners and when these needs are not addressed properly, this may lead to low academic performance and the decline of motivation of students (Sari et al., 2022).

Based on the literature reviewed from the preceding pages, there is a need to investigate the ways to help students adapt to the rigors of the transition from online to face-to-face mode of learning during this pandemic period (Bahinting et al., 2022; Ando et al., 2022). This can be done by looking into the academic attitude and behavior of the students while transitioning to the face-to-face mode of learning; this is then the purpose of the study. It is also the aim of this study to investigate the problems and challenges of the students as they face this transition in a physical set-up of the school. The coping mechanisms of the students in answer to their attitudes, problems, and challenges are likewise investigated. Specifically, this study investigates the attitude, problems, and coping mechanisms related to the said mode of learning transition of the junior high school students at St. Theresa's College of Cebu during the school year 2022-2023, the first year of the return to face-to-face classes. It is then expected that the results of this study may serve as a basis by which the teachers and guidance staff can lead the students towards a smooth transition from online to face-to-face mode of learning.

Research Questions

This study focused on understanding the behavior of students both desirable and undesirable toward transitioning from online to face-to-face mode of learning. Furthermore, the study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What are the desirable and undesirable attitudes and behaviors demonstrated by the students during the transition from online to face-to-face mode of learning?
2. What are the problems and challenges encountered during the transition from online to face-to-face mode of learning?
3. How do the students cope with the problems and challenges regarding the transition from online to face-to-face mode of learning?

Literature Review

Online classes give great benefits to the learners on their academic performance and give multiple relief to both parents and learners. Meeting in the virtual space costs less than meeting in person for learning continuity. For the learning process to continue despite the threat of the pandemic, the educational institutions and the teachers' innovative programs and educational services so that the learning process can continue to be fun, and interactive, and not create another burden to the parents and school children (Segarino et al., 2022; Cabello et al., 2021).

Gherheş et al. (2021) have stated that during the COVID-19 pandemic, online learning has turned into a substantial way for refining the traditional educational system and making innovations that would fit the new modalities of learning and will simultaneously meet the quality standards in education. Both teachers and students have had to change their behaviors, their teaching/learning styles, and their assessment methods (Flores et al., 2023).

However, the Department of Education said that face-to-face classes will be mandatory for public and private schools that offer basic education. This transitioning process has created a desirable and undesirable impact on the behavioral aspect of the students. According to Cranfield et al. (2021), the pandemic and its successive local and global 'lockdowns' have drastically changed the organizational

process of the educational system of higher education institutions. The learning experiences of the students at universities, their physical engagement, and attentive participation quantify more than having classes in the virtual space (Villar et al., 2022).

Research shows that there have been challenges and issues faced by the students during the transition period from online to face-to-face mode of learning. Gabriel et al. (2022) argue that in trying to move away from the traditional paper and pen environment (face-to-face), learning management systems (web-based learning environment to disseminate content) are one of the most highly adopted and used online environments in higher education institutions for e-learning (Delbo et al., 2023).

Many students who typically engage in face-to-face learning formats have now had to make a sudden transition to online learning. While there have been extensive discussions and analyses of the merits and challenges of online learning (Gimena et al., 2023; Gantalao et al., 2023), and research suggests that students typically enjoy taking online courses such learning is best when it is planned (or involves a gradual transition) and combined with other forms of learning. Ideally, students would often experience a blended learning environment, yet this is not possible in most instances due to the pandemic. It must also be acknowledged that students differ in their ability to thrive and flourish rather than struggle because of online learning (Mangubat et al., 2022).

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive qualitative research design. This design is appropriate in eliciting emergent themes coming from the experiences of the participants. Utilizing thematic analysis by Braun and Clarke can provide a clear picture of the attitudes and behaviors of the students during the transition from online to face-to-face mode of learning, the problems and challenges encountered during the transition from online to face-to-face mode of learning, and the students' coping mechanisms with the problems and challenges regarding the transition.

Participants

The participants (approximately 20 teachers) of this study are teachers who are currently employed at the Junior High School Department of Saint Theresa's College of Cebu during the school year 2022-2023. One of the qualifying factors to be a participant was the teaching experience during the pre-COVID-19 times, extending through the transition to the face-to-face mode of learning. The participants came from across all the grade levels of the Junior High School Department and from different subject areas. These were the inclusion criteria of this research.

The number of years of teaching experience of the participants ranged from three to twenty-one years. There were three males and seventeen females among the participants. All participants expressed their willingness to take part in the study.

Instruments

To gather data that would address the main problem of the study, questionnaires were given out to the teacher participants. The questionnaire was an open-ended one, with the respondents being free to formulate their terminologies and means of expression. The questions contained therein are as follows:

1. What are some desirable and undesirable behaviors have you observed among your students during the transition period from online to face-to-face mode of learning?
2. What problems and challenges have the students encountered during the transition to face-to-face learning mode?
3. What are the coping mechanisms manifested by the students regarding the problems and challenges faced?

Data Analysis

The data obtained were transcribed by one researcher; after which, the common denominators in the responses were categorized. The resulting and updated data were then turned over to a second researcher for review and further updating. This procedure contributed to the rigor of this research which will likely improve the validity and consistency of the study. A thematic analysis of the qualitative data gathered from the questionnaire was done. The significant statements were collated from each of the responses of all the teacher participants. In turn, meanings were formulated from these significant statements. The formulated meanings were then formed into cluster themes. The cluster themes were finally categorized into emergent themes.

The different constructs of the study were the attitude and behavior, problems and challenges, and the coping mechanisms of the students during the said transition period as observed, categorized and reported by their teachers. These responses by the teachers to the constructs of the study were arranged in a table format to be seen in the results of the study.

Results

The results are organized in the four tables that follow. The results of the study of the three constructs are contained within the first three tables respectively. The fourth table shows the summary of the emergent themes for each of the three constructs of the study.

Table 1. *Attitude and Behavior of Students during the Transition Period*

<i>Interview Questions</i>	<i>Frequency of Responses</i>	<i>Significant Statements</i>	<i>Formulated Meanings:</i>	<i>Cluster Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
Q1: What are some desirable and undesirable behaviors have you observed among your students during the transition period from online to face to face mode of learning?	3	SS1: Students are tech-savvy.	FM1: Improvement in the use of technology FM2: Attitude and behavior with regard to socialization FM3: Self-improvement and self-integrity FM4: Better engagement during classes and group activities FM5: Attitude and behavior in connection with learning difficulties	There are various and mixed attitude and behavior that are positive in nature.	Theme 1. There are desirable attitude and behavior displayed by the students during this transition from online to face-to-face mode of learning.
	1	SS2: More adept with technology			
	1	SS3: Development of research skills due to online exposure during the height of the pandemic.			
	1	SS4: Good grades for submissions			
	2	SS5: Consultation with teachers became easy and convenient.			
	5	SS6: Excitement to be in school.			
	2	SS7: Increased inquisitiveness			
	1	SS8: excited to see/meet their classmates/friends.			
	1	SS9: mindful and wary of the external environment			
	2	SS10: grateful for the efforts of the school to accommodate them.			
	1	SS11: Display independence			
	1	SS12: More responsible			
	2	SS13: Sense of fulfillment			
	1	SS14: Less cheating			
	1	SS15: Became conscious of cleanliness and hygiene.			
	1	SS16: some are adaptive.			
1	SS17: Increased student engagement during class discussion	FM4: Better engagement during classes and group activities	There are various and mixed attitudes and behaviors that are positive in nature.	Theme 2.	
1	SS18: Enthusiasm in the new environment				
2	SS19: Positive interaction during group activities				
1	SS20: More peer interaction some are happy when they do the activity correctly.				
1	SS21: energetic during activity time				
8	SS22: Student's short attention span and lack of focus				
6	SS23: Anxious to participate in class.				
3	SS24: Lack of retention and comprehension				
3	SS25: Lack of initiative to read/comprehend.				
3	SS26: Students have learning gaps and difficulty.				

1	SS27: Lack of comprehension and analytical skill		There are undesirable attitudes and behavior displayed by the students during this transition from online to face-to-face mode of learning.
1	SS28: Hard time in following instructions		
1	SS29: Not responsive during class		
1	SS30: Less interactive during class and group tasks		
3			
5			
1	SS31: Mediocre		
1	SS32: Cheating		
1	SS33: Easily gets tired.	FM6: Poor conduct and mannerisms	
1	SS34: Keep on complaining.		
1	SS35: Do not greet the teachers.		
1	SS36: Dependency on search engine became evident.		
1	SS37: Struggling to balance studies and online gaming.	FM7: High dependency on the use of technology	
1	SS38: Highly dependent on online sources to arrive at an answer.		
3			
4			
2	SS39: Gave a lot of excuses.		
2			
2	SS40: Easily distracted.		
1	SS41: Lack of motivation		
2	SS42: Boredom in class		
1	SS43: Incomplete and late submission		
1	SS44: Lack of diligence		
1	SS45: Lack of preparation		
1	SS46: Lack of time		
2	SS47: Do not take down notes.		
1	SS48: Absences	FM8: Poor self-discipline	
1	SS49: Some come sleepy.		
6	SS50: Decline self-discipline and time management skills		
1	SS51: Cannot sit down properly.		
1	SS52: Cannot keep area clean.		
5			
1	SS53: Talk and move a lot.		
1	SS54: Late in coming to school.		
1	SS55: Impatient, impolite		
1	SS56: Laziness		
1	SS57: Reluctant to socialize at first.		
1	SS58: Some students are introvert and shy while others are hype.	FM9: Psychological issues	
1	SS59: Experience anxiety, confusion, and self-doubt		
1	SS60: Low self-esteem at first, later on begin to accept new change.		

SS61: Uneasy due to short attention span
 SS61: Some are uncomfortable due to the new set-up.
 SS62: Some are not able to easily adjust.
 SS63: They were overwhelmed.
 SS64: overthinking

Table 2. *Problems and Challenges of Students during the Transition Period*

<i>Interview Questions</i>	<i>Frequency of Responses</i>	<i>Significant Statements</i>	<i>Formulated Meanings:</i>	<i>Cluster Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
Q2: What problems and challenges have the students encountered during the transition to face-to-face learning mode?	5	SS1: Lack of mastery of the subject matter		There are several problems and challenges faced by the students during this transition period.	Theme 1. Academic problems and challenges
	2	SS3: No desirable study habits			
	1	SS4: Low scores	FM10: Learning/academic problems and challenges		
	6	SS5: Low comprehension skill			
	1	SS7: Lack of teacher’s credibility by the student			
	3	SS8: Prerequisite topics which the students should already know have been forgotten.			
	1	SS18: Learning gaps			
	2	SS22: Increased workload for students- SS23: Poor communication skill			
	1	SS26: Plagiarism			
	1	SS9: Large class size which the students are not anymore used to.			
	1	SS10: Mixed ability class	FM11: Problems and challenges in physical set-up		
	1	SS13: Difficulty in catching and coping with the lessons.			
	4	SS20: Lack of preparation for F2F classes			
	1	SS2: Late submissions			
	3	SS6: Laziness in copying notes; take pictures of the writing on the board and of the Ppt.		Theme 2. Disciplinary problems and challenges	
	1	SS11: Tardiness			
	5	SS12: Poor conduct/ behavior	FM12: Problems and challenges attributed to discipline		
	1	SS15: Lack of focus			
	1	SS16: Time management			
	5	SS17: Difficulty in adjusting.			
1	SS19: Time constraints				
1	SS24: Distractions and procrastination				
1	SS25: Lack of cooperation by some members during group activities				
1	SS14: Finances	FM13: Financial problems and challenges			
1	SS21: Anxiety		Theme 3. Financial problems		
1		FM14: Psychological problems and challenges			
				Theme 4.	

Psychological problems and challenges

Table 3. Coping Mechanisms of Students during the Transition Period

Interview Questions	Frequency of Responses	Significant Statements	Formulated Meanings:	Cluster Themes	Emergent Themes
Q3: What are the coping mechanisms manifested by the students with regard to the problems and challenges faced?	1	SS1: Peer tutoring before quizzes	FM15: Formation of and joining in learning groups	Human interaction plays a very important role in most of the coping mechanisms exhibited by the students.	Theme 1. Academic coping mechanism
	1	SS4: Sharing notes through different platforms.			
	1	SS9: Dealing with activities that require group collaboration.			
	1	SS10: Motivation (effort and determination to finish)			
	4	SS14: Enrolment in remedial classes			
	7	SS15: Ensuring better class attendance in order to cope with the lessons.	FM16: Engaging in games, sports, and eating		Theme 2. Recreational coping mechanism
	4	SS7: Playing video games.			
	2	SS17: Engaging in sports			
	1	SS16: Stress eating	FM17: Organizing tools and methods that aid in learning		Theme 3. Discipline and organization
	2	SS2: Sharing of online review materials.			
	1	SS3: Organizing tasks.	FM18: Seeking the assistance of others for learning, expression of thoughts/feelings		Theme 4. Socialization
	1	SS8: Better time management			
	1	SS11: Making calendar of activities for deadline.			
	1	SS13: Prioritizing of tasks			
	1	SS5: Expressing thoughts/feelings to peers or teachers.			
	1	SS6: Socializing with friends			
1	SS12: Asking for teachers' assistance.				
1					
1					

Table 4. Summary of Themes

- Theme 1. Desirable attitude and behavior
- Theme 2. Undesirable attitude and behavior

The themes gathered from the responses of the participants could be categorized into desirable and undesirable attitude and behavior. The highest frequency obtained for the desirable attitude and behavior during the transition from online to face-to-face mode of learning was the excitement of returning to physical class. It can be said that the most desirable academic attitude and behavior obtained was the development of research skills as attributed from the online exposure of the students during the height of the pandemic. On the other hand, there are a number of undesirable attitude and behavior with the student's short attention span and lack of focus topping the list.

- Theme 1. Academic problems and challenges
- Theme 2. Disciplinary problems and challenges
- Theme 3. Financial problems
- Theme 4. Psychological problems and challenges

The themes gathered from the responses of the participants are grouped into academic, disciplinary, financial, and psychological problems and challenges. The problems and challenges on the academics ran first in the list of the said construct of the study. In particular, these academic problems and challenges include foremost the students' lack of mastery of the subject matter and the low comprehensive skills as compared during the pre-pandemic time.

- Theme 1. Academic coping mechanisms
- Theme 2. Recreational coping mechanisms
- Theme 3. Discipline and organization.

Theme 4. Socialization

The themes gathered from the responses of the participants are classified into academic, recreational, discipline and organization, and socialization coping mechanisms. Socializing with friends garnered the highest frequency among the coping mechanisms of the students. It is evident that the students would welcome assistance from their teachers since the students themselves approach their teachers for help. Academic coping mechanisms include peer tutoring and notes sharing. Recreational coping mechanisms include playing of video games during break time and engaging in sports as extra-curricular activities. Better time management and consistent class attendance are some of the classified coping mechanisms which deal with discipline and organization.

Discussion

Relative to the theoretical underpinning of this study, the stimulus for this study revolves around the transition from the online to the face-to-face mode of learning. According to Skinner, a given stimulus will lead to a behavioral response which in this study is paralleled to the attitude, behavior, problems, and challenges of the students during the transition period. Skinner further proposed that there corresponds reinforcement which in turn is aligned with the coping mechanisms of the students in this study.

For the Construct on Attitude and Behavior of the Students. There were two emergent themes derived from the results. The two themes were the desirable and undesirable attitudes and behavior.

There were four formulated meanings for this construct. The first was the attitude toward the improved use of technology (Emia et al., 2022). Academic-wise, this can be considered as the most desirable attitude and behavior wherein the teachers claimed that the students developed better attitudes towards research due to the online exposure at the height of the pandemic. The second formulated meaning was on the attitude and behavior concerning socialization (Redolosa et al., 2024). For this desirable behavior, the significant statement that garnered the highest frequency was the excitement of the students to go back to school. The third formulated meaning was on the attitude and behavior regarding self-improvement and self-integrity wherein the students now have negative attitudes towards cheating (Ugbamen et al., 2022). The fourth formulated meaning is on the attitude and behavior toward better engagement during classes and group activities (Cariaga et al., 2022). The developed positive attitude made the students participate more conscientiously during class discussions (Pableo et al., 2022).

The study on undesirable attitudes and behavior resulted in five formulated meanings. The first one was in connection with learning difficulties. As a result of this attitude and behavior, there was a short attention span and lack of focus among the students. The second formulated meaning was poor conduct and mannerisms wherein the students, as weeks went by, engaged in rampant cheating and plagiarism. The third formulated meaning is a high dependency on the use of technology. Ironically, what had used to be a desirable attitude on the use of technology, became a problem with the students engaging in plagiarism and online gaming even during class hours. Poor self-discipline, as the fourth formulated meaning, included late and incomplete submission of requirements by the student. Anxiety became the greatest psychological issue in the fifth formulated meaning.

For the Construct on Problems and Challenges of the Students. Certain academic problems and challenges of the students led to their lack of mastery of the subject matter and their low comprehension skills. This was included in the first formulated meaning. The students were no longer used to semi-crowded places such as a room with 40 students. This problem and challenge were included in the second formulated meaning related to the physical set-up of the classroom (Catulpos et al., 2024). Tardiness was included in the problems and challenges of discipline as the third formulated meaning. Financial problems and challenges landed as the fourth formulated meaning while anxiety as a psychological problem and challenge was part of the fifth formulated meaning (Binondo et al., 2023).

For the Construct on the Coping Mechanisms of the Students. The themes gathered from the responses of the participants were classified into academic, recreational, discipline and organization, and socialization coping mechanisms. Academic coping mechanisms included peer tutoring and notes sharing in the first formulated meaning. Engaging in sports, games, and eating as part of the recreational coping mechanism formed the second formulated meaning (Antipuesto et al., 2023). Better time management and consistent class attendance were some of the classified discipline and organization coping mechanisms in the third formulated meaning. Socializing with friends garnered the highest frequency among the coping mechanisms of the students in the fourth formulated meaning.

Conclusion

This study concludes that there are two emergent themes for the attitude and behavior of the students during the transition period. These themes are the desirable and the undesirable attitudes and behaviors of the students. The construct of the study on the problems and challenges of the students yields the following emergent themes, namely: academic; disciplinary; financial; and psychological. The third construct of the study on the coping mechanisms of the students results in the following emergent themes: academic; recreational; discipline and organization; and socialization. It can be noted that alignment of the results of the three constructs of the study can lead to a positive approach towards providing solutions to the problems and challenges brought about by the transition from the online to the face-to-face mode of learning.

Considering the research findings, it is imperative that to arrive at more reliable results, a greater sample size must be considered. Gomez et al.

Furthermore, it would be best that the participants should be the students themselves to have complete and direct information about the three constructs of this study.

To substantiate the written responses of the recommended student participants, a focus group discussion should follow the transcription of the written responses. A representative group from the entire sample size will have to be obtained for the focus group discussion.

The actual application of the findings of this study will provide essence to this research endeavor. It is, therefore, necessary that the results of this study be forwarded to the guidance office for their perusal. This study can aid the guidance office in formulating activities in altering positively the attitude and behavior of the students regarding the transition period towards the face-to-face mode of learning. The results of this study can also provide the basis by which the guidance office can design schemes that will help the students cope with the problems and challenges of the times. Coping mechanisms can also be suggested by the guidance office that are aligned with the attitude, behavior, problems, and challenges of the students. In so doing, the school will be able to better provide for the holistic education of the learners through significant improvement in the social, behavioral, psychological, and academic aspects of the lives of the students during this transition period.

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